

Approach of the NH_3 -TPD technique through the ammonia quantification by a wet chemical analysis

Enfoque alternativo de la técnica NH_3 -TPD mediante cuantificación del amoníaco por análisis químico húmedo

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Resumen

A fin de desarrollar un enfoque más accesible hacia laboratorios docentes y de investigación, se analizaron zeolitas HY, HMFI y HMOR con diferentes relaciones Si/Al mediante una técnica alternativa de NH_3 -TPD, basada en la cuantificación del amoníaco desorbido por vía húmeda. La técnica propuesta demostró un desempeño comparable a un equivalente comercial y su conveniencia para la enseñanza de los conceptos sobre acidez en sólidos y los fenómenos de fisiorción y quimisorción. La aplicación de la técnica alternativa NH_3 -TPD en zeolitas hidrotérmicamente desaluminadas permitió correlacionar los cambios en su fuerza y densidad ácidas con la intensidad del tratamiento hidrotérmico.

Palabras clave: acidez, NH_3 -TPD, enseñanza, zeolitas.

Abstract

To develop a more accessible approach to the docent and research laboratories, HY, HMFI, and HMOR zeolites with different Si/Al ratios were analyzed through an alternative NH_3 -TPD technique, with ammonia quantification by a wet methodology. The results show that the proposed prototype is comparable in performance to a commercial alternative and reveals it as a suitable method to teach concepts regarded to physical and chemical adsorption phenomena as well as acidity. The NH_3 -TPD applied to zeolites submitted to hydrothermal treatment conditions confirms the continuous decreasing of their acidic strength and acidic density.

Keywords: acidity, NH_3 -TPD, teaching, zeolites.

Highlights

Steamed zeolites were analyzed through an alternative NH_3 -TPD technique.
The ammonia quantification was performed by a wet methodology.
The changes in the acidic strength and density were successfully followed.
The performances from proposed and commercial techniques are comparable.
This alternative approach demonstrated its suitability to teaching and research.

Graphical Abstract

Introduction

Usually, acidity in solids is known as Brönsted or Lewis, associated respectively to surface acidic sites capable of giving protons to relatively basic species or capturing electrons from them. The adsorption of substrate molecules on the active acidic sites usually promotes their chemical transformation. The acid-catalyzed reactions have great industrial and environmental importance. Examples are Fisher esterification, acid-catalyzed transesterification, catalytic cracking, dismutation of xylenes, and others. The acidity is a significant property in adsorbents, and heterogeneous catalysts. For example, zeolites [1] constitute an interesting study subject due to their acidity, shape-selectivity, remarkable stability under

extreme conditions, and environmentally friendly nature.

The existence of framework tetrahedral aluminum atoms in the crystalline network is the main cause of the Brönsted acidity in zeolites. Then, incorporation or elimination of framework aluminum atoms through alumination and dealumination treatments affects the number and the strength of the acidic sites. Furthermore, when zeolites submit to high temperature (>673 K) hydrothermal treatments it occurs the combination of the resulting octahedral monomeric $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ species (Figure 1) with Brönsted acid sites, yielding an $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_2^+$ or AlO^+ cation (Figure 2). Several authors think those cations are the Lewis acidity carriers in zeolites [1].

Figure 1. Possible way of yielding of octahedral monomeric $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ species resulting from high-temperature hydrothermal treatments.

Figure 2. Combination of an $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ species with a Brönsted acid site, yielding an $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_2^+$ cation.

The mordenite [2] presents a relationship Si/Al higher than 5. Its orthorhombic crystal structure has two inter-connected systems of straight channels of an elliptical section, of about $6.5 \times 7.0 \text{ \AA}$, and $2.6 \times 5.7 \text{ \AA}$. Moreover, the zeolite HY [3], has a Si/Al ratio upper than 1.5 and a structure consisting of sodalite

boxes connected through hexagonal prisms that generate pores and cavities of about 7.4 \AA and 12 \AA .

The MFI (ZSM-5) zeolite is a pentasil-type zeolite [1], characterized by a low content of

aluminum ($\text{Si/Al} > 10$) and a medium pore size ($5.1 \times 5.7 \text{ \AA}$).

The BP-TPD (Temperature Programmed Desorption of basic probe molecules "BP") is a significant methodology for the study of the acidity of solid materials along with several techniques such as differential calorimetry, polynuclear NMR, and FTIR spectroscopy, among others. The basis of this technique is that the higher the acidic strength of the acid sites analyzed, the higher the heat of desorption of the basic probe molecules as ammonia or pyridine. Then, higher temperatures are needed to achieve the probe molecules' desorption. In chemistry teaching, BP-TPD can be an excellent medium to addressing concepts about physical and chemical adsorption and acidity in solids. However, because of its relatively high cost, TPD is not an available technique for many laboratories.

In a typical BP-TPD experiment, the acid sites from the analyzed solid are neutralized with molecules of a room temperature volatile basic probe substance as ammonia or pyridine. Then, the temperature rises with a constant speed, and the amount of desorbed base quantifies by an appropriate detection as Thermal Conductivity Detection or Mass Spectrometry. The representation of the detector signal as a function of the desorption temperature gives a profile which shape depends on the density of acid sites and their strengths distribution. Additionally, the acidic strength can be quantified from the desorption heats of the probe molecules calculated through the Amenomiya and Ketanovic equation (Eq 1) [4].

$$\ln\left(\frac{Tp^2}{B}\right) = \frac{Ed}{R \cdot T} + \ln\left(\frac{Ed}{R \cdot C}\right) \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Where B is the heating rate in K/min, Tp is the desorption temperature in K regard each summit, Ed is the desorption heat, C is a constant in min^{-1} related to each sample, and R is the universal gas constant.

Despite its usefulness, the BP-TPD analysis depends on the accessibility of the basic probe molecule to inner acidic sites, and cannot differentiate between Brönsted or Lewis acidic character.

In this work, several zeolites were analyzed through an alternative TPD technique, using NH_3 as a basic probe, to develop a more accessible approach to the docent and research laboratories.

Experimental Methodology

Preparation of the zeolite samples

The original HMOR zeolite (labeled OM) was obtained from 9 g of sodium mordenite (Union Carbide, Si/Al ratio of about five) through exhaustive ion-exchange for 24 h under agitation with 250 mL of 40% w/v NH_4NO_3 aqueous solution at a boiling temperature in a reflow assembly. Then, the exchanged ammonium–mordenite was filtered by suction and washed with 2500 mL of distilled water in portions of 500 mL. The resulting solid was then dried in a stove to 373 K for 24 h and calcined to 873 K for four 4 to yield the protonated-zeolite (OM). Portions of 0.4 g of OM were hydrothermally treated at 800 and 1000 K for 120 min with 100 % steam. According to the treatment temperature, the resulting solids were designated as M800 and M1000. The same treatment was applied to a NaY zeolite (Union Carbide, Si/Al ratio of about three) producing the OY, Y800, and Y1000 solids. The reticular Si/Al atomic ratios of the studied zeolites were acquired utilizing ^{29}Si -NMR characterization in solid-state in a Bruker AVANCE/300 MHz/7.0 T equipment at 59.62 MHz and 7.0 T.

The catalytic performance evaluates using the oleic acid esterification for 48 h at 403 K with a fast stirring rate. The conversion was calculated by Eq. 2:

$$X = (M_0 - M) / M_0 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

Where M_0 and M are the fatty acid concentrations at the beginning and at the t time.

NH₃-TPD analysis

Figure 3 shows the proposal of assembly for the NH₃-TPD analysis. To achieve precise control of temperature was used a Horizontal

Temperature Programmed Oven (Thermo Scientific, Lindberg Blue M TF55030A-1) with the capacity to reach over 1373 K. The oven host a Stainless Steel (SS) sample holder of about 5 cm, with input and output ports connect to 1/16 inch SS pipes. During the activation, and desorption of ammonia, N₂ (or He) introduces to the sample holder, and the gas pressure and flow are controlled through a manometer and a rotameter connected to a NaOH trap dryer. During the NH₃ saturation, ammonia delivers from a generator attached to a NaOH trap dryer by a U-shaped tube. Pass valves let to control the sequence of delivery of N₂ and NH₃ during the TPD experiment.

Figure 3. Scheme of the NH₃-TPD laboratory-constructed system.

Activation of the sample and adsorption of NH₃ before the TPD analysis

Each sample of 100 mg is previously grounded and sieved to particles of about 50 μm and placed into the SS sample holder. The activation was made from room temperature to 873 K with a 10 K/min increase rate under a 50 mL/min flow of dry N₂ at 101 kPa, holding this temperature for 15 minutes. Then sample lets reach room temperature under an N₂ flow of 25 mL/min.

Afterward, the sample saturates with NH₃ (50 mL/min and 101 kPa) for 15 minutes. In this approach, ammonia is supplied by a generator composed of an airtight 100 mL glass flask with about 30 mL of 25 % w/v NH₄OH (Fluka Riedel-de Haën). Ammonia leaves spontaneously at the beginning but soft heating of about 333 K could be posteriorly necessary. The ammonia carries into a solid NaOH drying trap connected to the sample holder input port. Ammonia that comes out of the sample holder allows bubbling in 40 mL of H₂SO₄ 0.05 mol/L,

with two drops of methylene-blue and methyl-orange indicator, until to reach a violet to green color change (after about 15 min). The excess of NH_3 removes with a 25 mL/min flow of pure N_2 introduced into the sample holder for about 30 min when there is no ammonia at the exiting gas, and there is only adsorbed molecular NH_3 on the sample. The absence of ammonia at the exiting gas can be confirmed by the neutral response of a High Precision Litmus or equivalent pH test strip. Meanwhile, 29 numbered 10 mL glass flasks must be thoroughly washed with distilled water and cured with 0.1 mol/L H_3BO_3 . Then, adds 2 mL of fresh 0.1 mol/L H_3BO_3 and 2 drops of bromocresol-green and methyl-red indicator [5] to each flask, yielding a pink color. Greenish-Blue (pH 5.4) - Light Pink (pH 4.5).

Temperature Programmed Desorption of ammonia

The TPD experiment begins at room temperature and a 10 K/min increase rate under a 50 mL/min N_2 feed flow. Simultaneously, flask number 1 places at the exiting tube end from the sample holder. After a 20 K temperature increase (two minutes), flask 1 is substituted by flask 2, and so on until it reaches 873 K. At the same time, must be made registration of the temperature interval regard each flask. Desorbed ammonia makes those flasks' solutions turn green. However, some of the last flasks could remain pink. The final temperature is held five minutes after the experiment is accomplished and then left down to room temperature.

Quantification

Each 10 mL flask with the complex $\text{NH}_4\text{H}_2\text{BO}_3$ titrates with an H_2SO_4 0.0025 mol/L standard solution, with a color change from green to pink at the final point. The quantity A_{Fi} of NH_3 in mmol regard to each

flask calculates from the spent H_2SO_4 according to the reaction:

Through the Eq. 4:

$$A_{Fi} = 2 \cdot V_{SAi} \cdot C_{SA} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

Where V_{SAi} , and C_{SA} , are respectively the spent volume in mL, and the molar concentration of H_2SO_4 standard solution.

Then, the specific quantity in mmol/g of desorbed ammonia from the sample is given by the summation:

$$A_W = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{29} A_{Fi}}{m_S} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Where m_S is the mass of the sample.

The specific quantity " A_W " in mmol/g of desorbed ammonia is related to the density of acid sites on the sample. The representation of A_{Fi} as a function of the desorption temperature led to a representative NH_3 -TPD profile of the distribution of the acidic sites according to their strength. There are usually two differentiated zones on the NH_3 -TPD profiles, corresponding to lesser (*l*-branch) or higher (*h*-branch) desorption temperatures than 573 K. There is agreement that *h*-branch comes from desorption of NH_3 bonded to surface strong acid sites. But, controversy persists over the origin of the *l*-branch [6,7]. Some researchers think that the *l*-branch comes from the adsorption of NH_3 on non-acid sites, but a significant number of authors consider that the relation between the *l*-branch and the acidity cannot be discarded. A possible origin [8] for the *l*-branch is NH_3 physically adsorbed on ammonium ions resulting from chemisorbed ammonia molecules on the acid sites or the direct desorption of NH_3 from surface weak acid sites.

Discussion

Comparative study

To prove its reliability, the performance of the laboratory constructed NH₃-TPD assembly compares with a commercial (Micromeritics TPD/TPR 2900) equipment,

on a Si/Al = 13 H-MFI zeolite (labeled MFI13), under the same conditions. As Figure 4 reveals, the superposed NH₃-TPD profiles match well, and the calculated densities of acidic sites too (Table 1, column 8, row 4).

Figure 4. Comparative image of two NH₃-TPD profiles of a Si/Al = 13 H-MFI zeolite taken under the same conditions. Dots: By the laboratory-built NH₃-TPD prototype. Continuous: By commercial equipment.

Table 1. Selected properties of the studied solids.

Solid	OM	M800	M1000	OY	Y800	Y1000	MFI13
Si/Al	6.29	20.81	>>41.27	3.14	4.11	5.13	13
X_{48h}	0.909	0.798	0.662	0.753	0.0882	0.0851	-
Acidity, mmol/g	2.32	1.34	0.651	2.55	1.75	0.698	1.180 (1.183)*
TCM <i>l</i> , K	473	453	453	436	433	-	433
TCM <i>h</i> , K	713	693	653	656	653	634	673

TCM: absolute temperature of the center of mass calculated through the integrated areas below the *l* and *h* branches. (*): acidity acquired through commercial equipment. Si/Al: calculated by ²⁹Si-NMR. X_{48h} : Conversion in the esterification of oleic acid at 403 K.

The Behavior of parental HMOR and HY zeolites and their derivatives

The M and Y series profiles (Figure 5), reveal the decreasing of the area below them at the growing intensity of hydrothermal treatment conditions, because of the diminution of polar Si-OH-Al groups associated with the Brönsted acidity and the

increase of extra-framework species, leading to the decrease in net acidity. In addition, there is a steady decline in the *h*-branch, suggesting a more rapid decline in stronger than weaker acid sites.

Figure 5. The NH_3 -TPD profiles from the M and Y series.

An additional peculiarity is the general tendency of the signals and the “temperature of the center of mass” (TCM) reckoned from the areas below the *l* and *h* branches to displace itself to lesser temperatures in solids treated at stronger hydrothermal conditions. This points out the progressive decreasing of the acidic strength (Table 1, rows 5 and 6). A comparison between solids submitted to equal hydrothermal treatment conditions reveals that TCM values are greater in M than the Y series; demonstrating that the mean acid strength is superior in the M than the Y series (Table 1, rows 5 and 6). Nevertheless, the density of acid sites is higher in the Y series than in the M (Table 1, row 4). The hydrothermal treatment leads to the diminution of polar Si-OH-Al groups associated with the Brönsted acidity and the increase of the Si/Al ratio by the segregation of the tetrahedral aluminum out of the crystalline framework as extra-framework species. On the other side, in both zeolite types, the diminution of acid sites density is accompanied by the diminution of the esterification activity (Table 1, rows 3 and 4), confirming the acidic nature of the active sites.

Conclusions

The profiles acquired under identical experimental conditions through the proposed laboratory-built NH_3 -TPD prototype and the commercial equipment are comparable, pointing out the reliability of the measurements from the acidic sites density and the strength distribution acquired through the proposed device.

The decreasing area below the NH_3 -TPD profiles evinces the diminution of the acidic density at more intense hydrothermal conditions. Such behavior coincides with the diminution of the bridged Si-OH-Al groups (associated with Brönsted acidity) by the transformation of the tetrahedral aluminum in extra-framework species because of the hydrothermal treatment. The accentuated decreasing of the *h*-branch confirms a faster decrease of stronger than weaker acid sites, agreeing with the general tendency of the NH_3 -TPD profiles to displace to lesser temperatures pointing out the progressive decreasing of the acidic strength. Although the acid density is higher in the studied faujasites than in the mordenites, the values of “center of mass temperature” (MCT) in the studied mordenites are higher than the faujasites subjected to the same hydrothermal treatment conditions. That

confirms the superior mean acid strength in the mordenite series.

The results place the NH₃-TPD as a suitable technique to teach concepts concerning physical and chemical adsorption phenomena as well as the acidity in solids.

References

- [1] Van Bekkum, H., Flanigen, E. M., Jacobs, P., Jensen, J. C. (2001) Introduction to Zeolite Science and Practice, 2nd ed., Elsevier, New York.
- [2] Meier, W. M. Zeitschrift für Kristallographie, 115 (1961) 439. <https://doi.org/10.1524/zkri.1961.115.5-6.439>
- [3] Hriljac, J. A., Eddy, M. M., Cheetham, A.K., Donohue, J.A., Ray, G.J. Journal of Solid State Chemistry, 106 (1993) 66 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1006/jssc.1993.1265>
- [4] Amenomiya, Y., Cvitanovic, R.J. The Journal of Physical Chemistry, 67 (1963) 144. <https://doi.org/10.1021/j100795a035>
- [5] Bremner, J. M., Mulvaney, C. S. 1982. Nitrogen Inorganic Forms. In: Methods of soil analysis. Part 2. Chemical and microbiological properties. Agronomy 9. ASA. SSSA, Madison, Wis. USA.
- [6] Zhao, Q., Chen, W. H., Huang, S. J., Wu, Y. C., Lee, H. K. and Liu, S. B. The Journal of Physical Chemistry, 106 (2002) 4462. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jp015574k>
- [7] Ma, D., Zhang, W. P., Shu, Y. Y., Liu, X. M., Xu, Y. D., Bao, X. H. Catalysis Letters, 66 (2000) 155. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1023/A:101909960702956>
- [8] Lónyi, F., Valyon, J. Microporous and Mesoporous Materials, 47 (2001) 293. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s1387-1811\(01\)00389-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/s1387-1811(01)00389-4)